

ELEVATED TEMPERATURE STRENGTH, AGING RESPONSE AND CREEP OF
ALUMINUM MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Aluminum matrix composites with reinforcement of planar-random graphite fibers, SiC whiskers, or alumina particulates have been evaluated for their high temperature performance. The composites were aged at 150 and 200°C for up to 500 hours. Microhardness results indicate accelerated aging of the composites in comparison with that of wrought 6061 Al resolutionized and aged under identical conditions. The aging response of the composites depends on the characteristics of the reinforcements. The graphite fiber reinforced composites and the silicon carbide whisker reinforced composites retain their tensile strength and stiffness in the overaged condition of the matrix. The composites were tested for their tensile stiffness and strength at temperatures of 150 to 350°C. The Young's modulus of all the composites remain relatively constant up to 350°C. Both the graphite fiber and silicon carbide whisker reinforced composites show substantial strength advantage over that of the wrought 6061 Al at all temperatures. The silicon carbide whisker and alumina particulate composites were evaluated for their creep behavior. These composites were subjected to creep deformation at temperatures of 232 to 350°C under stresses of up to 100 MPa. The whisker reinforced composite shows significant resistance to creep; about two orders of magnitude lower steady state creep rates than that of the wrought aluminum. The particulate composite had a moderate increase in creep resistance.

KEY WORDS: Particulate/Whisker/Fiber Composites; Matrix, Aluminum; Pressure Casting; Aging; Elevated Temperature; Creep.

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the primary attractions of metal matrix composites has been their potential for high temperature service (1-7). Signorelli (2) has reported that tungsten fiber reinforced superalloys (TFRS) offer a promising potential for a use-temperature increase for turbine components of up to 150°C above commercial superalloys. The unidirectional continuous fiber reinforced metal matrix composites, however, have relatively poor transverse strength (3,7,8), thus in applications where off-axis loading is significant the unidirectional composites are not useful. Cost of fabricating unidirectional composites is still high in comparison with that of the discontinuously reinforced metal matrix composites. In recent years there has been a resurgence of activity throughout the world to develop particle, whisker, or short fiber reinforced composites at a relatively low cost for commercial applications such as automotive parts (7,9-22). The widespread interest in developing low cost discontinuous reinforced composites can be primarily attributed to the following: the availability of relatively inexpensive silicon carbide whiskers produced from rice hulls (23-25); recent developments in casting-based techniques to fabricate composites in near net shapes (for example, see Ref. 7,26); and their amenability to be rolled, forged or extruded using conventional metalworking facilities with only minor modifications (16,18-22,27-32). For example, Tuler and Klimowicz (16) reported that the forging conditions for 15 volume percent alumina particle reinforced 2014 and 2219 Al are essentially the same as those for the unreinforced aluminum alloys. They further suggested that excellent forgeability is achieved in closed-die forging operations where the composite is under hydrostatic constraint. In general, the strength of the discontinuous reinforced composites is not substantially higher than that of the matrix metals or alloys; however these composites do show higher stiffness and wear resistance (7,26,33,34). Most publications describing the high temperature performance of the discontinuous reinforced composites deal with silicon carbide whisker reinforced aluminum (6,32,35-41). Some investigators have reported accelerated aging of silicon carbide whisker or particle reinforced aluminum composites (13,15,42-44). The accelerated aging response is attributed to the high dislocation density in these composites as a result of the large difference between the thermal expansion coefficients of the matrix aluminum alloys and silicon carbide whiskers or particles (13,43,45-47). Improved creep resistance of silicon carbide whisker reinforced aluminum composites have been reported by several authors (35-39). Brown (40) presented an overview of the relevant creep mechanisms in metal matrix composites. A potential increase of 50°C in the use temperature for silicon carbide whisker reinforced composites over unreinforced aluminum is suggested by Phillips (1). Similar results on other discontinuous reinforced composites such as alumina particle and short graphite or alumina fiber composites are almost non-existent. There is a general lack of comprehensive experimental results related to the high temperature performance of discontinuous reinforced metal matrix composites despite the tremendous interest in developing these composites for commercial applications. The objective of the present investigation is to determine the aging response, elevated temperature strength,

and creep resistance of selected discontinuous particle, whisker or short fiber reinforced aluminum matrix composites.

2. MATERIALS

Alumina particle reinforced aluminum composite ($V_f = 0.15$) was received from Dural Aluminum Company (San Diego, CA). The composite was fabricated by a proprietary casting method. Fused alpha phase alumina powders with mean particle sizes in the range of 8-14 microns were mixed into the molten aluminum alloy and then direct chill cast into billets. The billets were cut into smaller lengths followed by direct or forward extrusion at 350°C. The details of casting and extrusion can be found elsewhere (21,22). Silicon carbide whisker reinforced aluminum composite ($V_f = 0.20$) was received from Advanced Composite Materials Corporation (Greer, SC). The whiskers were introduced through a proprietary powder metallurgical method and hot pressed at a temperature near the solidus of the matrix. Subsequently, the billets were extruded and heat treated. Planar random graphite fiber (bilobal) composites were fabricated in this investigation using high pressure infiltration casting (HiPIC) (7,48-51). Pressures in excess of 100 MPa were used to rapidly infiltrate the fiber preforms with molten aluminum. Rapid solidification occurs as a result of the intimate contact of the composite with the die wall and an elevation in the solidification temperature of the melt. Wrought 6061-T6 aluminum was used as a reference material for its aging response upon resolutionization, elevated temperature mechanical properties and its creep behavior.

3. TEST PROCEDURE

The test procedures include heat treatment and microhardness measurements for studying the aging response of alumina particle, silicon carbide whisker, and planar random graphite fiber reinforced 6061 Al matrix composites. Tensile tests were done at room temperature and at elevated temperatures up to 350° C. Creep tests were done over a range of stresses and temperatures.

3.1 Age-Hardening The alumina particle and silicon carbide whisker reinforced composites were solutionized to eliminate prior work hardening due to extrusion. A ramping period of three hours (2.78°C/min) was used to obtain a stable solutionizing temperature of 530±5°C. This temperature was held for fifteen minutes and then the samples were immediately water quenched. The fabricated planar random graphite fiber reinforced aluminum composite specimens were subjected to identical solutionizing conditions. All composite specimens were placed into steel packets to minimize oxidation during heat treatment. The solutionized samples were aged for periods of 5 minutes to 3 hours at 200°C and for periods of 5 minutes to 500 hours at 150°C followed by air cooling. Vicker's microhardness was measured using loads of 80 to 800 g. Twenty values were typically obtained for the microhardness on each specimen.

3.2 Room Temperature Tensile Tests for the Aged Specimens The composite dogbone specimens were solutionized at 530°C followed by water quenching. The aging of these specimens was done only at 150°C. Aging times of the composites ranged from one hour to 500 hours. Strain gages were mounted onto the gage length to measure strains in the direction of tensile loading. Tensile testing was performed on an Instron with a 88.96 kN GR load cell. Load-displacement plots were recorded using a strip chart recorder and a strain indicator. A crosshead speed of 8.467×10^{-3} mm/s was used during the tensile testing.

3.3 Tensile Tests at Elevated Temperatures As-received alumina particle and silicon carbide whisker reinforced composites were tested at elevated temperatures ranging from 150°C to 350°C. The fabricated planar random graphite fiber reinforced aluminum composites and wrought 6061 Al were also included in the tensile testing at elevated temperatures. High temperature strain gages were mounted to determine accurately the Young's modulus and the ultimate tensile strength. Test temperatures were maintained within $\pm 5^\circ\text{C}$ of the desired set points. Thermocouples positioned next to the gage length were used to monitor the temperature during testing. A uniform temperature distribution was achieved throughout the composite specimen by soaking at the test temperature for 20 minutes prior to loading. High temperature testing was performed using the same testing equipment and crosshead speed as those used for room temperature testing.

3.4 Creep Tests Creep tests were performed only for the alumina particle and silicon carbide whisker reinforced aluminum composites using an 88.96 kN capacity Arcweld creep rupture machine. This machine is equipped with an automatic horizontal leveling arm and a three zone Arcweld furnace. The temperature of the furnace was monitored with three thermocouples; one located within the furnace, the other two next to the gage length. Displacements were measured by an LVDT attached to stainless steel grips. The creep tests were conducted over a temperature range of 232 to 350°C under stresses of 35 to 200 MPa.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Aging Response Figures 1 and 2 show the aging response (indicated by microhardness) of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3(\text{p})/6061$ Al and $\text{SiC}_w/6061$ Al, respectively, at temperatures of 200°C and 150°C. The aging response of wrought 6061 aluminum at 150°C is also shown in each plot. The aging response for both composites is accelerated compared to the unreinforced alloy. As expected, the lower aging temperature (150°C) produced higher maximum hardness after a longer aging time compared to the 200°C aging treatment. The peak microhardness values of the $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3(\text{p})/6061$ Al composite are 129 kg/mm² and 138 kg/mm², which reached after aging times of 1 hour at 200°C and 43 hours at 150°C, respectively. At the 150°C aging the wrought aluminum reaches its peak hardness of 111 kg/mm² at 55 hours. Thus the particulate composite shows moderate accelerated aging response in comparison with the matrix aluminum alloy (see plots for 150°C in Fig. 1). In contrast, the whisker composite shows a larger accelerated aging

FIGURE 1. Vickers microhardness of alumina(p)/6061 Al as a function of aging time at 150°C and 200°C tested under 400-800 g load. Wrought 6061 Al is given as a comparison (800 g load).

FIGURE 2. Vickers microhardness of SiC(w)/6061 Al as a function of aging time at 150°C and 200°C tested under 800 g load. Wrought 6061 Al is given as a comparison (800 g load).

response by reaching its peak microhardness of 148 kg/mm^2 at only 18 hours of aging at 150°C ; whereas the wrought aluminum reaches its peak microhardness 37 hours later at the same temperature (see plots for 150°C in Fig. 2). Figure 3 shows the matrix microhardness measured in the planar random graphite fiber reinforced 6061 Al composite specimens in two conditions: (a) as-cast composites aged at 150°C and (b) solutionization of the cast composites at 530°C followed by aging at 150°C . Lower loads were used to produce indentations small enough to occur only in the matrix and without touching any fibers in the plane of the measurement. Though the experimental results do not show a distinct microhardness peak for the graphite fiber composites, the matrix microhardness in the solutionized and aged composite exceeds the measured microhardness peak of unreinforced wrought aluminum. It can still be concluded that the matrix in the solutionized graphite fiber composites undergoes an accelerated aging as in the silicon carbide whisker composites.

FIGURE 3. Vickers microhardness of matrix in the solutionized and as cast Gr(planar random)/6061 Al as a function of aging time at 150°C tested under 80 g load.

4.2 Room Temperature Strength of Aged Composites The tensile strength and stiffness of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3(\text{p})/6061 \text{ Al}$ and $\text{SiC}_w/6061 \text{ Al}$ composites are presented in Figs. 4 and 5, respectively. Also included are the measured strength and stiffness of the unreinforced aluminum alloy. The strength of the composites first decreases upon aging and then increases with an increase in aging time, attains a maximum value followed by a gradual decrease with further increases in the aging time. It is important to note that the whisker composites not only show a higher level of strength but the high strength is retained for an extended period of aging time even when the matrix is in the overaged condition. The strength of the particulate composite is similar to the wrought unreinforced aluminum. The higher strength of the whisker composites is attributed to the approximate alignment of the whiskers during extrusion; the dogbone specimens were loaded in the extrusion direction. The stiffness of the composites first decreases upon aging and then remains almost constant for extended aging times. Only the whisker composite shows

higher stiffness over the wrought aluminum alloy. Figure 6 shows the mechanical properties of planar random graphite fiber reinforced aluminum composite ($V_f=0.20$) which was solutionized at 530°C and aged at 150°C. More experimental aging results are required to establish strength and stiffness peaks of the graphite fiber composite. However, considering the matrix microhardness (Fig. 3) and the strength and stiffness (Fig. 6) values it can be concluded that the graphite fiber composite may exhibit strength and stiffness peaks around 40 hours of aging at 150°C. The composite shows relatively small decrease in strength and stiffness after 100 hours of aging at 150°C signifying microstructural stability and fiber strengthening.

FIGURE 4. Ultimate tensile strength of SiC(w)/6061Al, alumina(p)/6061Al and 6061 Al when solutionized and aged at 150°C. As-received condition refers to extruded composites and 6061Al-T6.

FIGURE 5. Young's modulus of SiC(w)/6061Al, alumina(p)/6061Al and 6061 Al when solutionized and aged at 150°C. As-received condition refers to extruded composites and 6061Al-T6.

FIGURE 6. Ultimate tensile strength (a), Young's modulus (b) and failure strain (c) of solutionized bilobal Gr(planar random)/6061 Al as a function of aging time at 150°C.

4.3 Strength at Elevated Temperatures The particle, whisker and fiber reinforced composites were tested at elevated temperatures up to 350°C for their tensile strength. Results are presented in Figs. 7 and 8. The high temperature strength is primarily matrix dominated for the particulate and whisker composites; the strength gradually decreases with an increase in test temperature. The whisker composite clearly shows a higher use-temperature capability in comparison with both the particulate composite and the wrought aluminum alloy (see Fig. 7). The particulate composite behaves similarly to the wrought aluminum alloy. Planar random graphite fiber composites show that for the fiber volume fraction range ($0.20 < V_f < 0.30$) investigated they maintain their room temperature strength up to 350°C (see Fig. 8) signifying the effective fiber strengthening at elevated temperatures.

FIGURE 7. Elevated temperature tensile strength of SiC(w)/6061Al, alumina(p)/6061Al and wrought 6061Al-T6.

FIGURE 8. Histogram showing elevated temperature tensile strength of bilobal Gr(planar random)/6061 Al composites.

4.4 Creep Alumina particle and silicon carbide whisker reinforced aluminum composites were tested for their creep behavior at temperatures of 232 to 350°C under stresses of 30 to 200 MPa. Specimens tested at stresses over 100 MPa failed in less than 10 hours and the results were considered invalid for creep study. Table 1 includes the experimental conditions and the calculated steady state creep rates for the composites and 6061Al-T6. All the tests showed distinctly three regions: primary, secondary steady state, and tertiary creep behavior. In view of the long duration (up to 406 hours) of the creep tests, displacement versus time plots were reconstructed as it can be seen, for example, in Fig. 9 for the whisker composite. The plots clearly demonstrate higher creep rates at higher test temperatures while maintaining constant stress. Similar behavior was observed for the particulate composite. It is concluded that the whisker composites show higher resistance to creep in comparison with the particulate composite or wrought aluminum alloy (see Table 1). Our results indicate that the stress exponents (n) for the composites depend on the stress levels (see Table 2). The whisker composite shows a stress exponent of 16 at higher stresses. This implies high stress sensitivity and it is expected because of the higher elevation of local stresses at the whisker ends. The particulate composite in contrast shows a nominal stress exponent value of 5.7 at higher stresses as is expected for unreinforced aluminum alloys. The activation energies are 77 and 177 kJ/mol for the whisker and particulate composites, respectively. These activation energy values are lower than those reported by other investigators (35-39) who used solutionized composites for creep tests. We attribute the low activation energy values to the fact that in this investigation, creep tests were done on as-received work-hardened (see Fig. 5 and 6) composites having higher dislocation density.

Table 1. Steady State Creep rate for SiC_w/6061 Al, Al₂O₃(p)/6061 Al and 6061 Aluminum

Material	Temperature (°C)	Stress (MPa)	$\dot{\epsilon}_{ss}$
SiC _w /6061 Al	232	58.7	4.901×10^{-9}
	293	59.1	1.287×10^{-8}
	293	79.6	3.890×10^{-8}
	298	89.6	3.758×10^{-7}
	293	99.3	1.278×10^{-6}
	356	60.0	1.546×10^{-7}
Al ₂ O ₃ (p)/6061 Al	232	60.0	3.195×10^{-8}
	265	30.0	6.213×10^{-8}
	265	45.0	8.269×10^{-8}
	265	60.0	4.234×10^{-7}
6061 Al (Ref 36)	288	60.0	5.0×10^{-6}
	288	45.0	8.0×10^{-7}
	288	30.0	2.0×10^{-7}

FIGURE 9. Displacement vs testing time plots for the creep of SiC(w)/6061 Al under an applied stress of 60 MPa at three temperatures. The insert (100 MPa, 293°C) shows three-region creep behavior for 13 hours of test.

Table 2. Activation Energy and Stress Exponents for SiC_w/6061 Al, Al₂O₃(p)/6061 Al and 6061 Aluminum

Material	Activation Energy	Stress Exponent	Stress Range (MPa)
SiC _w /6061 Al	77 kJ/mol	16	80 - 100
		2.69	60 - 80
Al ₂ O ₃ (p)/6061 Al	177 kJ/mol	5.7	45 - 60
		0.7	30 - 45
6061 Al (Ref 36)	140 kJ/mol	~3	

5. CONCLUSIONS

6061Al matrix composites reinforced with planar-random graphite fiber, silicon carbide whisker, or alumina particle exhibit accelerated aging response as indicated by their microhardness. The tensile strength and stiffness of the planar random graphite fiber composite ($V_f=0.20$) only marginally decrease after 100 hours of aging at 150°C. The whisker composite ($V_f=0.20$) maintains high strength and stiffness even in the overaged condition. The high temperature mechanical properties of the particulate composite ($V_f=0.15$) are not different than the wrought aluminum alloy. In contrast, the whisker composite has a higher use-temperature potential; and the graphite fiber composite retains its room temperature strength up to 350°C. Steady-state creep rate is observed for whisker and particulate composites. The whisker composite is more resistant to creep in comparison with the particulate composite and the wrought aluminum alloy.

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